

Biliary Ileus as a Manifestation of Type V Mirizzi Syndrome: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Introduction: Mirizzi syndrome is defined as extrinsic compression of the common bile duct or common hepatic duct caused by various conditions, most commonly gallstones impacted in the gallbladder neck or cystic duct, as well as inflammatory processes such as chronic cholecystitis or biliary tract neoplasms (1). External compression may lead to erosion, fibrosis, or fistula formation. It is an uncommon condition, occurring in approximately 0.1% of patients with cholelithiasis (2). Type V Mirizzi syndrome, characterized by the presence of a cholecystoenteric fistula, represents one of the rarest and most complex variants. The most frequent fistula is cholecystocolonic, whereas cholecystogastric fistula is the least common. Between 5% and 28% of patients with this condition develop gallbladder carcinoma following cholecystectomy (3).

Case Presentation: We describe the case of a 64-year-old male with a history of untreated type 2 diabetes mellitus who presented to the emergency department with severe abdominal pain, one month of obstructive jaundice, and signs of acute abdomen. Laboratory studies revealed cholestasis and leukocytosis. Prior endoscopic management was non-therapeutic, and imaging studies suggested Type V Mirizzi syndrome. During exploratory laparotomy, a large gallstone associated with a cholecystogastric fistula was identified. Subtotal cholecystectomy and gastric repair with an omental patch were performed. The postoperative course was favorable.

Discussion: Preoperative diagnosis of Mirizzi syndrome remains challenging, particularly in advanced variants. In the presence of hostile anatomy and cholecystoenteric fistulas, subtotal cholecystectomy represents a safe alternative to reduce the risk of bile duct injury.

Conclusion: Type V Mirizzi syndrome requires a high index of suspicion and an individualized surgical approach. Subtotal cholecystectomy is an effective and safe option in complex cases, with favorable clinical outcomes.

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CASE REPORT

This is a 64-year-old male with a past medical history significant for untreated type 2 diabetes mellitus and a prior exploratory laparotomy 25 years earlier due to blunt abdominal trauma, which required intestinal resection with enteroenteric anastomosis; the specific bowel segment was not documented.

The patient presented to the emergency department with severe, generalized abdominal pain that impaired ambulation, absence of bowel movements, nausea, and vomiting. He also reported a one-month history of jaundice, diaphoresis, dark urine (choloria), and acholic stools. On physical examination, the patient was lethargic and markedly jaundiced. Abdominal

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examination revealed absent peristalsis, generalized tympanism, diffuse tenderness on palpation, generalized muscular guarding, and signs of peritoneal irritation.

Laboratory findings were as follows: hemoglobin 13.6 g/dL, leukocytes $18.6 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, total bilirubin 5.89 mg/dL, direct bilirubin 5.3 mg/dL, indirect bilirubin 0.56 mg/dL, and alkaline phosphatase 796 U/L. The patient had an external hepatobiliary ultrasound report (without available images), which described a common bile duct measuring 4.9 mm, a pear-shaped gallbladder measuring $6.8 \times 4.5 \times 3$ cm with a 2 mm wall thickness, and heterogeneous intraluminal content due to hyperechoic material without posterior acoustic shadowing, mobile with positional changes. The common hepatic duct showed density changes within the biliary tree suggestive of pneumobilia. An endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) performed externally two days prior to admission was non-therapeutic. External cholangiography identified a large gallstone, reported as Type V Mirizzi syndrome associated with cholangitis.

Given the presence of an acute abdomen, an exploratory laparotomy was undertaken for definitive surgical management. Intraoperatively, there was complete loss of normal anatomy at the cystic plate. Dissection along the gallbladder margin revealed a large intramural impacted stone associated with a cholecystogastric fistula extending to the lesser curvature of the stomach. A 10 cm gallstone was extracted. Subtotal cholecystectomy was performed due to difficulty identifying critical biliary structures. Gastric repair was carried out with primary closure reinforced with an omental patch. A nasojejunal tube was advanced into the jejunum to allow early enteral nutrition. Two drains were placed, one in the gallbladder bed and another at the site of the gastric repair.

Figure 1. Cholecystogastric fistula.

Figure 2. Extraction of a gallstone from the cholecystogastric fistula.

Following surgery, the patient remained hospitalized for postoperative monitoring. Enteral nutrition was initiated through the nasojejunal tube on postoperative day 1, with good tolerance. Three days later, oral intake was started as tolerated, which the patient also tolerated adequately; therefore, the nasojejunal tube was removed, and oral feeding was continued. The patient maintained adequate urine output throughout his hospital stay, and bowel movements resumed on postoperative day 2. Drain output was minimal, with no evidence of gastric or biliary leakage. On postoperative day 3, follow-up laboratory tests demonstrated normalization of bilirubin levels and resolution of leukocytosis.

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Figure 3. Large gallstone extracted from the cholecystogastric fistula.

The patient was discharged on postoperative day 7 due to clinical improvement. Four weeks after hospital discharge, an external magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) was performed, reporting postoperative changes consistent with partial cholecystectomy, a common bile duct measuring 7 mm without intraluminal filling defects, and adequate contrast passage.

Histopathological examination revealed gallbladder wall with granulation tissue and severe acute and chronic inflammation with evidence of prior hemorrhage (pyocystitis).

The patient demonstrated sustained clinical improvement, without abdominal pain, with adequate oral intake tolerance, normal bowel movements, and no evidence of jaundice. He was therefore discharged from the General Surgery service in stable condition.

DISCUSSION

Mirizzi syndrome is an uncommon complication of chronic cholelithiasis, characterized by extrinsic compression of the common bile duct or by the formation of fistulas between the gallbladder and adjacent structures. It remains a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge due to its variable clinical presentation, low preoperative detection rate, and the anatomical distortion frequently encountered during surgery (4).

The most widely accepted classification is that proposed by Csendes and Beltrán, in which Type V corresponds to the presence of a cholecystoenteric fistula. This type is further subdivided into Va (without gallstone ileus) and Vb (with gallstone ileus), as in our patient who presented with Type Vb

disease. This subtype represents one of the least frequent variants, with an estimated incidence of 1–4%, which explains the limited high-level evidence available to guide its management (5).

Preoperative diagnosis of Mirizzi syndrome remains complex. Clinical manifestations are often nonspecific, and conventional imaging studies have limited sensitivity. Although modalities such as ERCP and magnetic resonance

cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) have improved diagnostic accuracy, a significant proportion of cases—particularly advanced types (IV and V)—are diagnosed intraoperatively, when severe inflammatory changes and fistula formation markedly distort biliary anatomy (6), as occurred in our patient, who exhibited complete loss of normal gallbladder anatomy.

Surgical management remains the cornerstone of treatment, particularly in complex cases with fistula formation. In this context, subtotal cholecystectomy has gained relevance as a safe alternative when identification of the structures within Calot's triangle is impossible or hazardous. This approach reduces the risk of bile duct injury while resolving the obstructive and infectious process, as in the present case (4). Accordingly, subtotal cholecystectomy was performed because safe identification of biliary structures for total cholecystectomy was not feasible.

In recent years, minimally invasive and endoscopic strategies have been described with promising results in selected patients, particularly as bridging therapy or definitive management in high surgical-risk individuals. Some retrospective studies have reported high technical and clinical success rates in patients with Type IV and V Mirizzi syndrome treated endoscopically. However, available evidence remains limited, and the role of these techniques as primary treatment in complex fistulizing variants has not yet been clearly defined (7). In our patient, ERCP was unsuccessful due to the large size of the stone, which exceeded the dimensions amenable to endoscopic extraction.

Open surgical management continues to be required in a considerable number of Type V Mirizzi syndrome cases due to extensive inflammation, fistula complexity, and technical difficulty. Large surgical series have shown that although a laparoscopic approach is feasible in selected cases, conversion to open surgery or primary laparotomy does not significantly increase morbidity or mortality when management is individualized according to intraoperative findings (6). In our case, a laparoscopic approach would not have been feasible given the large stone size; therefore, an open technique was chosen.

The presence of cholecystoenteric fistulas entails additional clinical implications, including increased risk of biliary contamination, bacterial translocation, and infectious complications, underscoring the importance of meticulous surgical management and close postoperative surveillance (8).

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Nevertheless, in our patient, resolution of the obstructive process led to a decrease in systemic inflammatory response markers and an uneventful postoperative course.

In conclusion, Type V Mirizzi syndrome is a rare but clinically significant entity. Cholecystogastric fistula, as observed in our patient, is particularly uncommon. Early recognition, multidisciplinary planning, and individualized selection of surgical strategy are essential to minimize complications and optimize outcomes, as delayed treatment may result in sepsis and multiorgan failure.

CONCLUSION

Type V Mirizzi syndrome is an uncommon entity, and the cholecystogastric variant is particularly rare, as in our patient. It is associated with high surgical complexity and is frequently diagnosed intraoperatively due to marked anatomical distortion and severe inflammatory changes. Its management requires careful evaluation and an individualized surgical strategy.

In the present case, subtotal cholecystectomy combined with repair of the cholecystogastric fistula allowed safe resolution of the clinical condition, preventing bile duct injury and achieving a favorable postoperative outcome. This approach should be considered a valid alternative when safe identification of biliary structures is not feasible.

The presentation of this case adds to the existing literature and underscores the importance of timely recognition, appropriate surgical planning, and intraoperative flexibility in decision-making to optimize outcomes in patients with advanced Mirizzi syndrome.

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